

THE EFFECT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON JOB SATISFACTION AND TURNOVER INTENTION AMONG CENTRAL SCHOOL ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN ORMOC CITY DIVISION

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Teacher turnover remains a critical issue in the Department of Education, Ormoc City Division, affecting school stability, instructional quality, and student learning outcomes. This study examines the relationship between Human Resource Management (HRM) practices, job satisfaction, and turnover intention among teachers in three central elementary schools. Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), the study evaluates key HRM strategies, including compensation, work environment, and professional development, and their impact on teacher retention. Findings reveal that current compensation practices do not effectively reduce turnover intention unless they lead to higher job satisfaction. Additionally, a positive working environment significantly enhances job satisfaction and decreases turnover rates. The structural model results emphasize the strong direct and indirect effects of HRM practices on teacher commitment. The study underscores the need for increased investment in better teaching facilities and resources to improve workplace conditions. Practical recommendations include revising HRM policies to enhance job satisfaction, implementing targeted interventions to reduce teacher attrition costs, and conducting further research on the influence of national policies on teacher retention. By bridging gaps in understanding HRM's role in education, this study provides valuable insights for policymakers and administrators in strengthening teacher retention strategies.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a significant role in education by facilitating the learning process, benefiting both the learners and society. The significant component of the Department of Education, Ormoc City Division, is the two thousand two hundred eleven (2,211) teaching personnel in one hundred (100) public schools of the basic education curriculum. Educational infrastructure is nothing when the basic and crucial component of the learning process is not on board. For various reasons, manifestations of burnout from highly trained and competent teachers have concerned the school and division management. Official leave of office and resignation of teachers have greatly affected administrators to promptly address the added ancillary and teaching load delegation to other faculty members. Seventeen teachers reportedly leave their positions during the school year 2020-2021 at an unusual time, according to the Human Resource Management Office (HRMO). The numbers do not substantially impact the whole organization but rather the stability of schools where the position was vacated, the teaching loads, and most significantly, the overall well-being of teachers and the learners left behind.

The improvement of performance in schools largely depends on teachers' job satisfaction. This implies that schoolteachers' job satisfaction would positively enhance the student's learning, as much as teacher job satisfaction has many important and far-reaching implications. First, it contributes to well-being as satisfied teachers are less susceptible to stress and burnout (Toropova 2019). In addition, there is evidence that students of teachers who are content with their job also feel better (Collie & Perry 2019). Furthermore, satisfied teachers offer higher instructional quality and better student learning support (Kunter et al 2013). Finally, content teachers demonstrate stronger job commitment and are less prone to leave the profession (Blomeke et al 2017), which is especially in times when teacher turnover is high. On the other hand, unsatisfied teachers are not likely to produce good results and would negatively affect the student's performance.

The increasing teacher turnover rates and a subsequent decrease of highly trained and qualified teachers is a growing concern in DepEd Ormoc City

Division. Data from records showed that the Human Resource Management Office (HRMO) is overwhelmed with teachers manifesting burnout and frustrations, and 17 highly trained and competent teachers have resigned for various reasons from January 2021 to February 2022. The intention to leave any organization with complete willingness is called turnover intention (Alias et al 2018). In other words, turnover intention means quitting a job (Lazzari et al 2022). When teachers are conceded, the process of learning is defeated. Hence, teachers are the primary concern in every Human Resource Management (HRM) Department of Education. Human resource management (HRM) is the managerial action and duty of developing and retaining competent employees. Human Resource Management Practices (HRMP) deal with how people are employed and managed in a particular organization. It has a solid conceptual basis drawn from the behavioral sciences, strategic management, human capital, and industrial relations theories (Armstrong 2010). This foundation has been built with a multitude of research studies. Most organizations refer to HRM as involving people practices. The role of HRM in the Department of Education is critical in enhancing teachers' experiences and motivating them to contribute more to the organization.

However, the differing, contradictory, and conflicting research findings about human resource management practices and their relationship to faculty job satisfaction and turnover intention necessitate further study to understand HRM practices in Ormoc City Division and job satisfaction and turnover intention among faculty members. Many faculty members have left Ormoc City Division rather than stay committed to the overarching educational goal before the year-end school rites of 2022. This is a significant source for stakeholders within the school districts of Ormoc City, given the high cost associated with recruiting and training new teachers. There is a dearth of evidence and information on the role of HRM practices on job satisfaction and turnover intention among teachers in the Philippines. Moreover, a teacher affects the cost associated with recruiting and training new staff and minimizes the school district's capacity to ensure effective teaching to all students. This study will be one of the few local studies that will be conducted to assess the effect of Human Resource Management Practices on job satisfaction and turnover intention in the Department of Education (DepEd) in Ormoc City Division. This study will investigate the HRM practices adopted by the Department of Education (DepEd) Ormoc City Division and determine the relationship of HRM practices on job satisfaction and turnover intention of the teachers from three (3) central elementary schools.

The findings of this study will be significant not only for the Department of Education Ormoc City Human Resource Management but also for other sectors, as it will allow them to look closely at some indicators of the presence the HRM practices that may have a significant effect on employees' job satisfaction and turnover intention. According to Paşaoğlu (2015), there is a significant reason to understand employees worldwide that appreciate human resource practices in another context.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted with ethical considerations such that participants should not be subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Respect for the dignity of research participants was prioritized. Full consent was also obtained from the participants before the study. An adequate level of confidentiality of the research participants was warranted, and the anonymity of DepEd personnel in Ormoc City Division teaching personnel and research data gathered for the objectives of this study were ensured.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Human Resource Management Practices

HRM practices have become increasingly significant to the academe and practice these past few years because HRM methods aid in developing employees' attitudes and actions (Kooji & Boon 2018). Human resource management (HRM) practices mediate the relationship between HRM strategy and organizational results. The organization signifies attaining goals and objectives because of Human Resource Management (HRM).

According to Elrehail et al (2020), management is responsible for human resource practices, and applying these processes and procedures directly affects the optimization of employees' effectiveness to achieve their full potential. Management scholars have exerted continuous efforts to study more about human resource practices and how these practices enhance employees' performance and achieve organizational goals (Rasool et al 2019). Many studies examine the role or relationship of HR practices, employee job satisfaction, and turnover intention. Employee training, performance assessment, collaboration, employee engagement, and remuneration were the five practices investigated by Pule et al

(2014). They discovered a satisfactory correlation between HR practices and overall organizational success because HRM practices engage in different processes and procedures that are established and implemented, aiming to create high-performance employees (Smith & Markwick 2009).

The influence of human resource practices is an essential component of human resource management and organizational psychology (Vermeeren et al 2014). In this regard, teachers who are satisfied with the HRM processes and procedures apparently will contribute to attaining goals and objectives. Happy employees lead to lasting work dedication and commitment to retaining employment. Human resource management (HRM) practices may be a key source of employee satisfaction, resulting in less absenteeism, lower turnover, and increased employee loyalty to organizations (Ijigu 2015).

Training and development as related to job satisfaction and turnover intention

Training & development is the process through which an organization or institution delivers professional development activities to improve individuals' knowledge, abilities, and attitudes to execute their tasks efficiently (DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2011). This practice is one of the four core HRM systems of the Department of Education. It is considered the heart of the Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in HRM (PRIME-HRM) because it addresses the basic criteria of every organization's recruitment, participation, efficiency, commitment, and loyalty.

External variables, teachers' attitudes and views, a lack of experience, a constrained perspective, and individual interests all impact the accomplishment of education's overarching goals. To ensure the success of educational goals and, consequently, national development, teachers' training and development should be formed in ways that cater to their needs (Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular 10, s. 1989 & CSC MC 28, s. 1990). According to Bowers (2017), training is critical to help employees gain new knowledge, skills, and attitudes (KSA) to sustain standard performance in a competitive environment. A study by Amos & Natamba (2015) indicated that training positively affects employee performance and improves employee engagement and enthusiasm. In short, training and development have a significant and positive relationship with job satisfaction and turnover intention.

In the academe, training & development is an essential factor in human resource management practices that might significantly affect job satisfaction,

influencing turnover decisions (Nawaz & Pangil 2016). However, some studies have claimed that training and development might increase employee turnover by improving employees' knowledge, skills, and attitudes, making them more appealing to competing organizations (Jehanzeb & Bashir 2013).

Compensation/pay practice as related to job satisfaction and turnover intention

Compensation/pay is a human resource management practice that generally refers to remuneration, salary, and benefit. These practices play an essential role in HRM strategies. High pay and benefits relative to other industry players attract and retain performing employees, though it might impact the management's overall labor costs. Generally, compensation/pay practice is a crucial indicator of employee job satisfaction. A study by Mabaso & Dlamini (2017) affirmed the significance of compensation in employee job satisfaction.

Research evidence found that compensation is essential in determining employees' job satisfaction, reducing their intention to leave. Some studies reported that higher compensation or wage reduces firms' turnover and recruitment costs (Mudor & Tookson 2011). In other words, compensation is negatively related to turnover intention and recruitment costs. If the employees have higher compensation, the organization should have a lower voluntary turnover (quits). Hussain (2020) discovered a significant negative association between pay and intention to leave. Silaban and Syah (2018) asserted that salary reasonably contributes to job satisfaction and employee retention. The employees cited a competitive salary as a critical motivational variable influencing their turnover decision. Yang & Lin (2014) validated that compensation practices significantly affect employees' job satisfaction. Reza and Alam (2022) confirmed the positive relationship between compensation and employee satisfaction, whereas (Iqbal et al 2022) found a substantial effect of salary and employee retention decisions.

In a school setting, Kumar (2019) argued that compensation satisfaction is a significant construct for companies and human resource management. Because pay practice is a vital mediator between an organization's compensation policy and pertinent behavioral and attitudinal outcomes. The association of compensation with job satisfaction influences the motivation of employees, which affects organizational effectiveness and efficiency. The extent of how negatively or positively it affects total organizational outcome is still vague in a formal educational setup.

Creating a positive working environment as related to job satisfaction and turnover intention

A positive working environment of a school organization is a motivation for its teaching and non-teaching personnel. Oludeyi (2015) defined the working environment as a composite of three sub-environments: technological, human, and organizational. The technical environment of a school organization refers to the Department of Education's school equipment, technological infrastructure, and other physical features that make it simpler for staff to perform their duties and tasks.

The human environment composes the employee relations among the peers or co-teachers and management. The human environment is designed to enhance formal and casual interactions in the school to share best practices, knowledge, and ideas. The organizational environment includes enabling mechanisms like procedures and systems that support the Department of Education's ideals and principles. Thus, a positive working environment is created by management for the betterment of all the personnel in the organization. Organizations boost employee performance by creating favorable working conditions. As a result, employee job stress and burnout are minimized, employee job satisfaction is improved, and employee turnover intention is curbed (Salama et al 2022). Job dissatisfaction caused by a poor working environment may reduce employee commitment, influencing the decision to leave (Vangel 2011).

Working environments have beneficial and unfavorable effects on teachers' job satisfaction and turnover intentions. Diverse studies on various working populations have revealed that perceived work conditions significantly influence turnover intentions (Nicolas et al 2016). According to the authors, if employees' expectations of the organization are not met, the consequences for job satisfaction and commitment to work result in employees deciding to leave the organization. Teachers are the implementing arm of the DepEd organization. Retaining the normalcy of the school's working environment and the overall well-being of teachers is paramount to HRM's streamlined practices.

HRM Practices and Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on the job, which acts as a motivation to work. The term job satisfaction was brought to the limelight by Robert Hoppock in 1935. Hoppock described job satisfaction as any

combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances in that the person truthfully says, "I am satisfied with my job" (Rajput et al 2016). It is a significant factor in any organization and extensive team management. It is a factor that induces employees to work with long-term commitment. Job satisfaction is also about the teacher's sentiments or mental state regarding their duties and responsibilities. This concept supports employee procedures, practices, and undertakings (Guest 2017; Johari et al 2019).

Integrating HRM practices, such as compensation, training & development, and the actual working environment in which teachers perform their duties can all impact job satisfaction. Employee well-being manifests positive attitudes evidenced by utmost effectivity and efficiency toward performance (Yunikawati et al 2021). Studies have indicated that HRM strategies may be an evident remedy for motivating personnel's knowledge, abilities, and attitude, impacting teachers' job satisfaction and overall organizational performance. Related research has also found a direct and positive relationship between human resource practices and job satisfaction (Uddin et al 2017). Employing happy employees is vital for all types of organizations. Happier employees tend to be more productive and innovative, which would help to sustain organizational dynamics. As a result, human resource managers must consider ways to improve employee well-being. Managers must keep abreast of factors that influence human behavior in all organizational policies, programs, and activities intended for the most critical asset ever to exist in an organization (Mehrez & Bakri 2019).

HRM Practices and Turnover Intention

Turnover is when an employee leaves his post, job, and title, and the organization replaces them (Belete 2018). Turnover intention is a measurement of how organizations do about employees' plans to leave their positions – voluntary nature; or organizations plan to remove employees from their work - involuntary nature. Although the turnover intention may not always convert into quitting, it is a good predictor of termination in many cases (Hom et al 2017). Turnover is one of the investigated phenomena in human organizational behavior. Due to its psychological and economic dimension and organizational implication, the trend draws attention. Hence, HRM managers must know that several factors are essential to thwarting turnover intention and decisions. Such factors include and are not limited to attitudes, pay practices, knowledge, training, and development, and creating a positive working environment but all-encompassing variables.

Teachers' turnover intention increases when they evaluate their present jobs and compare them with better ones in another workplace. From the standpoint of organizational finance, an increase in the number of teachers leaving their existing position raises human resource transactional and transitional expenses. It may disrupt normal operations and lead to unsustainable working conditions, teamwork dynamics, and performance from a sustainability standpoint. Thereby causing workplace issues and an imbalance (Fernandez-Docallas 2021). Human Resource Management practices in the Department of Education may correct school issues and teachers' attitudes significant to turnover intention. Thus, organizations' HRM managers need to beat turnover intention by understanding the standard ground of PRIME-HRM (CSC MC No. 24, s. 2016). The societal contributions of elementary teachers in the community and the role of HRM practices in influencing turnover intentions is an exploration of issues and evaluation of neglect in the teaching force. In the context of the Department of Education, anticipating turnover intention among teachers is overlooked and disregarded. The challenge of the HRMO in the Department of Education is to retain and use the potential of talented teachers. According to Waitiu (2013), teacher turnover is a widespread issue and a complicated phenomenon that has frequently been linked to either a problem with personnel planning or a sign of low teacher morale and motivation. Human resource management should use practices that increase emotional attachment to the organization, creating teachers' sense of moral obligation to stay in the organization (Iqbal et al 2022).

Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

The ultimate emotion experienced by humans after completing work is job satisfaction. It relates to how much work satisfies people's fundamental requirements, is in line with their expectations and values, and will function effectively. The degree of job satisfaction appears to be correlated with some workplace factors, including turnover, productivity, and absenteeism. Most studies have found that workers with fewer absences were happier with their jobs. According to Shah and Jumani (2015), job satisfaction is the best predictor of turnover intention.

A study conducted by Toropova (2019) concluded that there is a strong relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and turnover intention with HRM practices indicators. It is significantly noted that teachers' job satisfaction influenced students at all schools at every level. Besides, this was equally

important for teachers as civil servants, educational managers, and employees. This also predicted teachers' retention and contributed to school effectiveness (Mason & Matas 2015). Yet another study highlighted that there were many factors associated with the higher rates of turnover. Among them were inadequate school administration support, student discipline problems, limited faculty input into school decision-making, and low salaries (Shuls et al 2020). Toropova (2019) said that given that teacher shortage is an international problem, teacher job satisfaction merits closer attention. Not only is job satisfaction closely related to teacher retention, but it also contributes to the well-being of teachers and their students, overall school cohesion, and enhanced status of the teaching profession (Tayyar 2014).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. The study's conceptual framework is anchored on the research conducted by Omar Aburumman et al (2019). It shows the independent variables, sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents, HRM practices, specifically training and development, pay practices, creating a positive working environment, and dependent variables, level of job satisfaction and turnover intention of teachers.

The sociodemographic constructs may significantly influence job satisfaction and turnover intention among teachers. Demographic variables distinguish one from another, as these variables may be individual origins or are related to the work of the individual in the organization. These characteristics include gender, age, nationality, job experience, and job level. The overall relationship between HRM practices and staff is weakened and strengthened by demographic factors because men are not as female, the older is not as younger, the employee with ten years of experience is not as new, and so on (Alsaiani et al 2020).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

HRM practices act as negotiators between management strategy and outcome. These are internally set human resource policies and practices implemented to ensure the achievement of organizational goals. DepEd policies on training and development, compensation (pay practices), and a positive working environment is a streamlined organization process (Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 24, s 2016). Training and development (T&D) is an essential practice in which the management can assist employees in gaining new knowledge and skills to maintain standard performance in this dynamic environment.

Compensation (pay practice) is a systematic approach to providing monetary value to employees in exchange for work performed. For almost two decades, public school teachers in the Philippines—the largest army in government service—have gained continued improvements in their compensation. The average teacher in the Philippines is getting paid more with the Salary Standardization Law of 2019 or under Republic Act 11466, of which the fourth tranche is expected by 2023. Schools must attract, develop, and retain

effective teachers to deliver high-quality education. Working conditions play an important role in a school's ability to do so because the working environment is also considered the "students' learning environment." Positive working conditions reduce teachers' job stress and burnout. DepEd has been addressing the working conditions of teachers, the call for de-loading of non-teaching tasks and unnecessary paperwork, upgrading their salaries to at least SG 15, providing ample and timely benefits, and allocating bigger funds to education are all factored in creating a positive working condition of teachers in the Philippines. These policies and provisions in the law, through Orders and Memoranda, are constantly provided and updated to cater to the warranted needs of field teachers. Teachers may attribute their behavioral and attitudinal perspectives to T&D, pay practices, and the working environment.

In general, when inducements are increased by an organization, this will lower the tendency of the employee to leave and vice versa. And the reason for leaving could have been prevented by the organization. Human resource management infers that workers are assets of the organization, and the expectancy theory predicts that one level of motivation depends on the attractiveness of the rewards sought and the probability of obtaining these rewards can hold DepEds' objective to achieve the educational agenda. Researchers found that job satisfaction plays an intervening role between service quality and performance (Dasilveira et al 2020). Job satisfaction mediates the influence of learning and development, compensation and working environment on turnover intention.

In this study, we use the definition of job satisfaction provided by Happock (1935), who describes job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that cause the person to say, "I am satisfied with my job truthfully." Indicators of job satisfaction used in the study are the HRM's current policies streamlined into practices such as compensation or pay practices, the working conditions not limited to physical state but as well as employee relations, and organizations' training policies and programs. Also, teachers' job satisfaction has many important and far-reaching implications. The first benefit is that it improves overall well-being since contented teachers are less prone to stress and burnout (Toropova 2021). Evidence supports the notion that happier teachers are likewise happier with their work as educators (Song 2021). Additionally, happy teachers provide their students with greater learning assistance and higher-quality education (Toropova 2021). Finally, content teachers are more dedicated to their jobs and are less likely to abandon teaching (Thomas & Hammond 2019), which is critical in periods of high teacher turnover.

Teacher turnover comprises interrelated perceptions of teacher migration and attrition, where migration describes teachers moving to other schools, while attrition pertains to teachers leaving the profession altogether (Toropova et al. 2021). However, regardless of the type of turnover, there are always negative consequences for a particular school from which a teacher is departing. Ronfeldt, Loeb, and Wyckoff (2013) suggest a disruptive impact of turnover beyond compositional changes in teacher quality, especially in lower-performing schools. Besides affecting student learning and motivation, teacher turnover negatively affects faculty collegiality and trust and leads to a loss of institutional knowledge, which is critical for supporting student learning. In the end, overall school performance is affected.

3. METHODOLOGY

Locale and Respondents of the Study

This study was conducted in Ormoc City, Leyte, Philippines, particularly the Central Elementary Schools of the Department of Education (DepEd), Ormoc City Division, Region 08. Ormoc City Division is considered a medium division in terms of the number of teachers, schools, and district population. Ormoc City Division consists of 10 Districts, with one central elementary school in each District. The total number of teaching personnel is 2,211. The target participants of this study were teachers from the top 3 central elementary schools with the most faculty members.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Purposive sampling was applied in selecting the schools for this study. Purposive sampling is a technique extensively used for identifying and selecting information-rich cases to make the most use of limited resources (Palinkas et al., 2015). This entailed locating and choosing individuals or groups who were particularly knowledgeable about or experienced with a topic of interest. The top 3 central elementary schools with the most teaching personnel were the criteria for selecting this study's schools. First, the sample size of teachers was determined using Slovin's statistical formula. After determining the sample size, the teacher-respondents were selected using proportionate random sampling. The sample size was computed as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + Ne^2)} \quad (1)$$

where:

n = sample size

N = total population

e = error margin or margin of error;

With a 95 percent confidence level or a 5% significance level, a sample size of 130 was obtained from 193 teachers. The population was based on the SY 2021-2022 inventory profiling of teaching personnel of the Planning Section in the Ormoc City Division. These three central elementary schools have the greatest number of teaching personnel. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents for the study.

Table 1. Distribution of the sampled teacher respondents.

Schools	Population (a)	Percent (b)	Respondent (a×b)
Ormoc City Central School	95	49.22%	64
Linao Central School	51	26.42%	34
Ipil Central School	47	24.35%	32
Total	193	100 %	130

Data Collection Procedure

This study gathered primary data using the survey questionnaire. First, the researcher seeks approval from the school’s division Research Committee and Schools Division Superintendent to gather respondent data. After securing the necessary approval, the survey questionnaire was distributed to school heads (school management) of the three (3) central elementary schools. A “drop and pick me later” approach was utilized in gathering the survey questionnaires to give the respondents adequate time to answer the questionnaires without disrupting classroom activities. For follow-up questions, the researcher connected with the respondents via mobile phone. This also conforms to the safety and health protocols of Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) and the Ormoc City Local Governance Unit in Covid19 countermeasures.

Data Analysis

Responses from the survey were encoded in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (IBM, SPSS) statistical software. A descriptive summary of the sociodemographic characteristics and response to HRM practices are presented in tables and figures in the results and discussion section. Also, the correlation analysis is provided to investigate the potential association between HRM practices and the teacher respondent's job satisfaction and turnover intention. According to Creswell (2012), researchers employ a correlational study design to describe and assess the degree of a link between two or more variables or set scores. This helps assess the effect of HRM practices on job satisfaction and turnover intention among teachers from central elementary schools in the Ormoc City Division. The identified indicators for a construct measure will be tested for validity. The validity tests will be used to assess how well the identified indicators for a construct will measure the expected construct or assess the extent to which a factor or a construct is distinct from other constructs (Hair 2019).

On the other hand, the relationships of HRM practices presented in the conceptual framework are tested using the Partial-Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The PLS-SEM has been the standard approach in testing complex interrelationships of variables in a model like the conceptual framework presented in Figure 1 (Hair 2017; Schuberth et al. 2022). Moreover, PLS-SEM is widely applied in organizational, marketing, strategic and international management (Hair et al. 2020; Hult et al. 2018; Khan et al. 2019). Hence, the applied methodology to answer the study's research objectives is highly applicable. The PLS-SEM analysis was employed using the SEMinR package (Ray et al. 2022) and data visualization using the ggplot package (Wickham 2016) using the R programming.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sociodemographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 summarizes the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents. The average teaching experience among sampled teachers in Ormoc was 16 years. At the same time, the majority of the interviewed teachers were in the age group of 40 – 49, which takes the largest share of the total sampled teachers in Ormoc. In comparison, 26 percent of the sampled teachers are near the

retirement age with a range of 50 – 59 years old. The observed age distribution from the randomly sampled teacher in Ormoc reflects the aging population of teachers in the country and validates the claim of UNESCO that “countries with older teachers need to step up recruitment; those with younger teachers must think about policies to retain existing teachers.” And a study of Swedish teachers finds that the lack of support from administrators and student discipline issues are more important than pay. A declining number of Filipinos prefer to take degrees related to teaching. As the results show, younger teachers in Ormoc between 20 – 29 and 30 – 39 only make up 15 and 23 percent of the sampled teachers, respectively. The shortage of teachers and the unavailability of teaching facilities could threaten the vision of the country’s educational sector in providing quality education.

In terms of gender, the majority are female teachers, while male teachers are only 11 percent of the total sample. This can be attributed to teaching, which has long been associated with women due to the ideological link between women’s domestic roles and careers as schoolteachers (Ullah 2016). Whereas in recent years, the representation of teachers belonging to the LGBTQ+ community has been increasing. Although the observed share of LGBTQ+ teachers is only 4.6 in Ormoc, it is considered a significant change compared to previous years. This gradual increase of LGBTQ+ representation in teaching is part of promoting inclusivity in the work environment.

On the other hand, the majority of the teachers are married, and most of the respondents (80 percent) have 1 – 3 children. While 23 percent of the respondents have no children, 11 percent have 4 – 6 children. On the other hand, the respondents’ position varies from being a head teacher (4.5 percent), to a master teacher (10.6 percent), and ninety-six of the respondents (85%) are in the entry position of the teaching profession. The observed proportion of teachers in each position reflects the competitive qualifications required in the teachers’ promotion. As the Department of Education is revising the basic qualification standards of each position in the teaching profession, this entails a new set of requirements for selection, recruitment, and promotion (PRIME HRM).

Table 2. Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents.

Variables	Count (%)	Percent
Age		
20-29	19	15
30-39	30	23
40-49	47	36
50-59	33	26
Gender		
Female	110	85
Male	14	11
LGBTQ+	6	4.6
Civil status		
Married	101	80
Separated	1	0.8
Single	17	13
Widowed	8	6.3
No of children		
0	27	23
1-3	73	63
4-6	13	11
14	1	0.9
15	1	0.9
22	1	0.9
No of years teaching ^a	16	9
Position		
Head teacher 2	3	2.7
Head teacher 3	2	1.8
Master teacher 1	10	8.8
Master teacher 2	2	1.8
Teacher 1	20	18
Teacher 2	35	31
Teacher 3	41	36
Educational attainment		
Baccalaureate	57	44
Masteral degree	73	56

^a mean (standard deviation)

Human Resource Management Practices

The organization's cultural and environmental conditions could influence its members' perceived job satisfaction and turnover intention (Yousef 2017). Similarly, understanding teachers' perceptions regarding HRM practices of the Ormoc City Division is crucial in determining the level of job satisfaction and turnover intention among teachers. Thus, the sampled teachers' responses related to HR practices are summarized in Figure 2, while respondents' perceptions of job satisfaction and turnover intentions are presented in Figure 3.

As shown in Figure 2 for the indicators related to training and development, 66 percent of the respondents agreed that training and development policies are being established. A similar percent share of responses is observed for other indicators related to training and development provided by the HRMU in DepEd Ormoc City Division. Whereas indicators under compensation and pay practices, the study found that 55 percent of teachers agreed that attractive compensation and 58 percent perceived salary increase is crucial to staying committed and dedicated in the current position. As pointed out by UNESCO (2015), the intrinsic benefits of teaching are shaped by factors such as compensation, pay practices, and rewards. These can impact teachers' job satisfaction, tasks, and job nature as well as teachers' ability to do their work well and engage with students.

The overall importance of a positive working environment is embodied in Zig Zigler's (2023) quote: "Positive thinking will let you do everything better than negative thinking will." Applying this principle in the workplace can improve productivity and the quality of work (Weiss 2018). Moreover, among sampled teachers' 30 percent strongly agree that they are happy about the positive relationship between school administrators and other teaching staff. At the same time, 64 percent of the teachers consider their current workplace a safe environment. In addition, 69 felt a sense of autonomy in performing their work. Several management studies considered that a sense of autonomy could be vital to the modern organization (e.g., Chester Barnard, 1938; Mary Parker Follett, 1926; Elton Mayo, 1933). Frederick Taylor (1911) emphasized that scientific management was a "mental revolution" for workers that would occur when management and worker interest were aligned. Theorists have long emphasized autonomy as a fundamental priority for employees that organizations must meet.

Figure 2 (a-c). Teachers' perceptions on HR practices

Teachers' perceived job satisfaction and turnover intention

Teachers perceived job satisfaction and turnover intention is summarized in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The study found that more than half of the respondents agreed that they were satisfied with their present work, the training policies and programs, and the compensation/pay practice and felt a high morale in their current work. In addition, 65 percent of the sampled teachers are satisfied with their working environment, including physical and employee relations.

Although each organization defines job satisfaction otherwise, there must be a consensus on common themes. These themes include job satisfaction and pride in their organization, the degree to which individuals love and believe in what they do for a living, and the view that their organization values what they bring to the table. The more engaged an employee is, the more likely he or she is to "go the extra mile" and offer outstanding on-the-job performance (Ćulibrk J, Delić M & Mitrović S et al. 2018).

Figure 3. Teachers' perceived job satisfaction

In addition, the study found that satisfied employees are more likely to commit to staying in their current organization. Only 2 percent of the respondents strongly agree to be unsatisfied with the organization's working conditions, training and development programs, and organization pay practices. This would

suggest that the respondents are more likely to be satisfied with the policies and programs regarding the Human Resource Management practices of the Department of Education. Also, 2 percent of the respondents will likely consider transferring to another organization when unsatisfied with the HRM practices mentioned previously. Lastly, 61 percent of the respondents are willing to accept any assignment to keep working for DepEd. This can be attributed to teachers' values aligned with the organization, which may have driven teachers' willingness to go beyond what is expected to achieve the same goals or objectives.

Figure 4. Teachers' perceived turnover intention.

Assessment of the measurement model

Factor Loading

An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted before the PLS-SEM estimation to identify items that measure the presented factors (e.g., turnover intention, job satisfaction, and HRM practices). The EFA aims to identify the items that reflect its intended factor and serve as measurement indicators.

A maximum likelihood estimation with a varimax rotation was used during the factor extraction in the EFA process. Table 3 presents the final group of

items used to indicate its intended factors and corresponding factor loadings using the EFA. The factor loading indicates how much of the variation of the items is explained by the factor. Higher factor loadings indicate items are good indicators of their expected factor (i.e., HR practices, job satisfaction, turnover intention). Factor loadings exceeding ± 0.70 indicate a well-defined structure and are the goal of any factor analysis (Hair, 2019; Zwick & Velicer, 1986). For example, in TI1, the factor loading is 0.95 ($0.95^2 \sim 0.90$), and the result indicates that 90% of the item's (TI1) variance is explained by the factor Turnover Intention. Across all items, the original and bootstrapped factor loading exceeds the recommended threshold.

Table 3. Bootstrapped factor loadings.

Factor	Indicator	Original estimate	Bootstrap means
Turnover intention	TI1	0.950	0.951
	TI2	0.959	0.958
	TI3	0.971	0.971
Job satisfaction	JS1	0.904	0.903
	JS2	0.847	0.844
	JS3	0.806	0.804
	JS4	0.878	0.877
	JS5	0.850	0.848
Positive working environment	PWE1	0.915	0.913
	PWE2	0.823	0.820
	PWE3	0.899	0.898
	PWE4	0.774	0.774
Compensation practices	CP1	0.930	0.931
	CP2	0.929	0.929
	CP3	0.758	0.749
Training and development	TD1	0.719	0.702
	TD2	0.884	0.881
	TD3	0.907	0.905
	TD4	0.888	0.887

Factor Reliability and Validity

Construct reliability or factor reliability assesses the extent to which a group of items is consistent in what it intends to measure. The test aims to assess whether the items selected are statistically reliable. The reliability measurement used is Cronbach’s alpha, Rho A and Rho C, as shown in Table 4. These reliability measurements share a similarity in terms of what they represent. Thus, the interpretation of the test is the same (Hair et al., 2020). Higher values indicate a higher level of reliability. Reliability values of 0.70 and above are satisfactory as a good measure of reliability. Results show that all factors are above the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating that items used to measure the factors are reliable.

Accordingly, convergent validity assesses how well the identified items as indicators for a construct to measure the expected construct. For example, job satisfaction was measured using five indicators, and construct validity can be used to determine how well those five indicators measure the job satisfaction factor. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is a measurement for convergent validity. An AVE greater than 0.50 provides evidence for convergent validity (Hair, 2017, 2019). Results show that AVE for all factors is above the recommended threshold of 0.50, indicating that the measured factors passed the convergent validity test.

Table 4. Reliability and convergent validity of factor measurement.

Construct	Cronbach’s alpha	Dijkstra-Henseler's (rho A)	Composite reliability (rho C)	Average variance extracted
Turnover intention	0.958	0.973	0.985	0.922
Job satisfaction	0.910	0.933	0.912	0.736
Positive working environment	0.875	0.915	0.882	0.730
Compensation practices	0.850	0.908	0.914	0.768
Training and development	0.874	0.914	0.898	0.727

Note: Alpha, RhoA, and RhoC should exceed 0.7, while AVE should exceed 0.5

Discriminant Validity

The discriminant validity of a component or concept measures how different it is from other constructs. The idea is to identify unique items as measurements for an intended factor. If the selected items uniquely measure the intended factors, then that factor should not be highly correlated to other factors.

The Fornell-Larcker and heterotrait-monotrait criteria are the most used measurements for discriminant validity. The italicized and bolded values are the AVE of each factor. At the same time, non-bolded values are the inter-correlation of the factors. To establish discriminant validity, the off-diagonal values (i.e., non-bolded values) should be less than AVE (i.e., values in bold) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As shown in Table 4, across all the elements in the Fornell-Larcker matrix, the factor's AVE is greater than its correlation to other factors. The results imply that the items used in measuring its expected factor are unique relative to other measurement indicators of other factors. Using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the test of discriminant validity is established.

Table 5. Discriminant validity using the Fornell-Larcker criterion.

	TI	JS	PWE	CP	TD
Turnover intention (TI)	<i>0.960</i>				
Job satisfaction (JS)	0.077	<i>0.858</i>			
Positive working environment (PWE)	0.097	0.839	<i>0.855</i>		
Compensation practices (CP)	0.155	0.466	0.488	<i>0.876</i>	
Training and development (TD)	0.233	0.618	0.648	0.378	<i>0.853</i>

Note: The Fornell-Larcker criteria table reports the square root of AVE on the diagonal (italicized and bold values) and constructs correlations on the lower triangle. The factor's AVE should be higher than its correlation with other factors.

To establish the discriminant validity using the heterotrait-monotrait criterion (HTMT), the HTMT value should be lower than the recommended threshold of 0.90 or less than 0.85 for a more conservative threshold (Henseler et al. 2015). When the HTMT value is high (above 0.90), it may suggest that one or some indicators in one construct is highly related. It means the construct is not conceptually distinct. Using the HTMT criterion summarized in Table 5, values

are below 0.90 or 0.85, which suggests that constructs passed the discriminant validity test.

Table 6. Discriminant validity using heterotrait-monotrait criterion.

	TI	JS	PWE	CP	TD
Turnover intention (TI)					
Job satisfaction (JS)	0.102				
Positive working environment (PWE)	0.104	0.939			
Compensation practices (CP)	0.166	0.514	0.553		
Training and development (TD)	0.261	0.679	0.725	0.440	

Note: To establish discriminant validity using the HTMT criterion, the value should be below 0.90 or less than 0.80 for a more conservative threshold.

Structural Model

Drivers of Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

Using the partial least-square structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM), the study estimated the direct and indirect effects of HR practices on teachers’ perceived job satisfaction and turnover intention. The structural model shown in Figure 5 illustrates the relationship of the factors related to HR practices, while the indirect and the total effects are summarized in Table 6. The values measure the magnitude of the relationship and the sign to the direction of the relationship.

In terms of the compensation practices, results found that the direct effect of the compensation practices is positive. This implies that better compensation is positively associated with higher perceived satisfaction among teachers. While the observed direct effect is not statistically significant, the result still provides an important insight into the possible impact of improving teacher compensation. For example, in Indonesia, Siregar and Maryati (2020) found that salary was positively and significantly related to job satisfaction and negatively and significantly affected turnover intentions. Moreover, Barch and Cherng (2021) concluded that overall, teachers’ job satisfaction persists when teacher salary satisfaction is considered. As teacher salary satisfaction provides the most tangible rewards for teachers’ services and their primary source of livelihood, teachers are more satisfied with their job when they are more satisfied with their salaries.

On the other hand, the direct effect of compensation practices on turnover intention implies that current compensation practices do not lower the turnover intention among teachers. However, looking at the indirect effects of compensation practices as mediated by job satisfaction, the study found adverse indirect effects on turnover intention. The results imply that if the compensation practices resulted in higher perceived satisfaction among teachers, better compensation does indeed lower the turnover intention among teachers. This can be attributed to compensation in the form of income or salary as one of the main determinants of how fulfilling a teaching career could be. Across different occupations, income has been the main reason for employment, which suggests that it keeps people motivated despite difficulties faced at work (Casinillo et al., 2022). In such instances, if teachers are equally rewarded for their work experiences, teachers that are content with their jobs are motivated to stay in the organization.

In the case of teachers in Ormoc City Division, the turnover intention may have been caused by job dissatisfaction partly due to the pay practices of the Department of Education. Under the Republic Act 11466 (i.e., Salary Standardization Law of 2019), Teacher 1 salary starts at 27,000 pesos, approximately 6% higher than in 2022. Compared to other Asian countries, teachers' entry-level position and salary is comparatively lower. As a result, records from HRMO showed that teachers who resigned or terminated their contracts have substantial training and experience, making them marketable to other countries.

Figure 5. Estimating the effects of HR practices towards teachers' job satisfaction and turnover intention using the partial least-square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM).

Consequently, a positive working environment is positively associated with higher job satisfaction. It implies that creating a positive and safe working environment could lead to higher satisfaction in the teachers' workplace. For instance, Ansley et al. (2019) found that high cases of teacher turnover in elevated-need settings is not due to problems with their students' needs but rather to excessive stress and dissatisfaction with work caused by unfavorable working conditions. With teacher shortages worldwide and high attrition rates, satisfied teachers give help to school systems because they are healthier, more productive, and more likely to keep their job in the long run. Dreer (2021) exposes the link between job-related well-being and job satisfaction. The findings imply that teachers' job-related well-being, particularly pleasant emotions, plays a significant role in job satisfaction and subsequent retention.

The study found a negative association regarding the direct effect of a positive working environment on teachers' turnover intention. The result implies

better working environment is associated with a lower intention to seek alternative jobs among teachers. In addition, the indirect effects of a positive working environment as mediated by job satisfaction reveal a negative effect towards turnover intention. Both the direct and indirect effects of a positive working environment help in the perceived intention of teachers to stay committed to their teaching jobs. It is also important to note that a positive working environment has the largest magnitude of impact in increasing the perceived job satisfaction among teachers compared with other HR practices.

The study results found that the working environment is one of the most important influencing factors in job performance and satisfaction in an organization. However, monetary incentives are insufficient to motivate employees to achieve higher levels of performance and job satisfaction (Torlak 2019). For instance, Glassdoor’s Mission & Culture Survey (2019) when it comes to job satisfaction, over half of the 5,000 respondents said that organizational culture is more important than money. In contrast, DepEd is a huge organization, and equitable provision of a positive working environment to all 500,000 employees remains challenging. If the unsatisfactory working environment continues in the DepEd division, it will be more challenging for the management to curb the increasing turnover intention.

Table 7. Direct, indirect, and total effects of HR practices towards teachers’ job satisfaction and turnover intention

Factors	Effects	Job satisfaction	Turnover intention
Job satisfaction	Direct		-0.114
	Indirect		
	Total		-0.114
Positive working environment	Direct	0.729	-0.060
	Indirect		-0.083
	Total	0.729	-0.143
Compensation practices	Direct	0.065	0.126
	Indirect		-0.007
	Total	0.065	0.118
Training and development	Direct	0.121	0.295
	Indirect		-0.014
	Total	0.121	0.281

A positive working environment has a favorable influence on employee commitment. For example, the study by Zhenjing et al. (2022) determined that a healthy work environment fosters a loving and pleasant work atmosphere that encourages employee dedication, and workers are loyal to their employers. Therefore, employee commitment has the potential to enhance the employees' job performance. This can be attributed to employees showing a higher level of job performance when they are committed to their employer or organization.

Aside from the time allotted for the preparation of instructional materials, teachers allotted a significant amount of time to attend training and development activities. Participation in these activities allows the accumulation of knowledge, skills and attitude required for the teachers' promotion. Moreover, participation in training and development may effectively motivate employees and improve organizational performance. The study found that training and development activities positively affect job satisfaction. However, training and development increase teachers' turnover intention. The education department has a well-structured training program designed to address the specific needs of different positions and specialities of participants. However, teachers who left their position during the pre-COVID-19 are highly trained, competent and have been in the organization enough to earn a badge as "experienced wise" in the profession. The application of training and development has been their ticket to leave the organization and make them more marketable across countries where teacher turnover intentions are also a problem.

On the positive side, the study showed that the increased participation of teachers in training and development activities improves teachers' job satisfaction. The training and development activities may lower the turnover intention. The results imply that the effects of training and development indirectly lower job turnover intention. The observed results can be attributed to employees responding reciprocally toward the organization's investment and demonstrating stronger commitment. Previous research has looked at the training-to-turnover intention connection, and various findings have been reached. According to reciprocity theory, training can lead to more commitment and reduce employee turnover. At the same time, there are situations where employees may not share the same motivation for professional growth and development, which has contributed to inconsistencies in the findings about the relationship between the presence of training and development programs and organizational commitment (Wang et al. 2020). A dedicated employee links their principles with the essential values of the organization, resulting in a long-term connection. Misalignment of

basic beliefs and resistance to change may raise employee turnover intentions (Rawashdeh & Tamimi 2019).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the present study highlighted the importance of human resource management practices in an organization in determining teachers' job satisfaction and turnover intention. At the same time, study results contributed to the scant research on the relationship between HRM practices, socio-demographic characteristics, job satisfaction, and turnover intention.

The study concludes that current compensation practices being implemented by the Department of Education need to be reviewed, as the results found that it does not effectively lower teacher turnover intention. The results demonstrated that compensation practices must be translated to higher perceived satisfaction among teachers before it will have a decreasing turnover intention effect. Increased investment in improving the teaching facilities and resources must be prioritized in improving the quality of education and a better workplace among teachers. The study found a high magnitude of the effect of a positive and better working environment for higher job satisfaction and lower turnover intention. Both the direct and indirect effects of a positive working environment help in the perceived intention of teachers to stay committed to their teaching jobs.

Finally, the study contributed to bridging the gap in understanding the importance of better HRM practices in job satisfaction and turnover intention among teachers in the Department of Education. The practical implication of the present study sheds light on the current condition of the central public schools experiencing alarming turnover intention. The study found that better HRM practices translate into higher level of job satisfaction and lower turnover intention. Based on the findings of the study, the recommendations are made:

1. The educational sector should focus on developing and reforming best HRM practices that will contribute to higher perceived job satisfaction to lower the increasing turnover of teachers. As the result demonstrated, unless DepEd interventions translate to job satisfaction, higher turnover intention among teachers will persist.

2. DepEd Ormoc City Division should provide appropriate interventions for holding teachers' turnover decisions to write off costs during hiring, selection, training, and development.
3. A further in-depth study needs to be conducted, particularly on the possible impact of the national policies on the relationship between DepEd HRM practices, job satisfaction and turnover intention.
4. Also, given that the study was limited to three HRM practices, future studies may explore other DepEd HRM practices (e.g., hiring and selection and performance appraisal).

6. REFERENCES

- Alias, N. E., Rohmanan, N. H., Ismail, S., Koe, W., & Othman, R. (2018). Factors influencing turnover intention in a Malaysian manufacturing company. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(10). <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i10.3171>
- Ajayi, S., & Olatunji, O. (2017). Demographic analysis of turnover intentions amongst Nigerian high school teachers. *Australian and International Journal of Rural Education*, 27(1), 62–87.
- Akter, T., & Fakhrul, M. (2018). Impact of demographic factors on the job satisfaction: A study of private university teachers in Bangladesh. *SAMS Journal (India)*.
- Alsaiani, A., Puteh, F., & Ali, A. (2020). Could demographic variables impact the relationship between HRM practices and employee loyalty? A meta-analysis review. *Human Resource Research*, 4(1), 205.
- Ansley, B. M., Houchins, D., & Varjas, K. (2019). Cultivating positive work contexts that promote teacher job satisfaction and retention in high-need schools. *Journal of Special Education Leadership*, 32(1).
- Amos, K. J., & Natamba, B. (2015). The impact of training and development on job performance in Ugandan banking sector. *Journal on Innovation and Sustainability*, 6, 65–71.
- Ayesha, Y. (2013). Effect of compensation factors on employee satisfaction—A study of doctors' dissatisfaction in Punjab. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 3(1), 142–157. ISSN 2162-3058.
- Armstrong, S. (2010). *Handbook of human-resource management practice* (11th ed.). Human Resource Management International Digest.

- Arnoux-Nicolas, C., Sovet, L., Lhotellier, L., Di Fabio, A., & Bernaud, J.-L. (2016). Perceived work conditions and turnover intentions: The mediating role of meaning of work. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7.
- Bayo-Moriones, A., & Merino-Díaz de Cerio, J. (2002). Human resource management, strategy, and operational performance in the Spanish manufacturing industry. *M@n@gement*, 5, 175–199.
- Belete, A. (2018). Turnover intention influencing factors of employees: An empirical work review. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 5(7).
- Blömeke, S., Jentsch, A., Ross, N., Kaiser, G., & König, J. (2022). Opening up the black box: Teacher competence, instructional quality, and students' learning progress. *Learning and Instruction*, 79, 101600.
- Bowers, A. J. (2017). Quantitative research methods training in education leadership and administration preparation programs as disciplined inquiry for building school improvement capacity. *Journal of Research on Leadership Education*, 12(1), 72–96.
- Carver-Thomas, D., & Darling-Hammond, L. (2019). The trouble with teacher turnover: How teacher attrition affects students and schools. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 27(36).
- Casinillo, L. F., & Paradero, A. L. (2022). Review of socio-economic research and development studies. *Research Article On Modeling*, 6(1), 39–56.
- Chandrasekaran, M., & Gayathri, R. (2019). A study on job satisfaction level of employees.
- Cherng, H. Y. S., & Barch, F. (2021). Teacher work conditions and satisfaction across school configuration and contexts. *Global Education Monitoring Report Team*. ED/GEMR/MRT/2021/P1/02.
- Chirchir, R. (2016). Demographic factors and job satisfaction: A case of teachers in public primary schools in Bomet County, Kenya. *Journal of Education & Practice*, 7(3).
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, evaluating, quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Pearson Education Inc.
- Collie, R., & Perry, N. (2019). Cultivating teacher thriving through social-emotional competence and its development. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 46.
- Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 10, s. 1989. Establishing the personnel development committee (PDC).

- Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 28, s. 1990. Reiterating certain policies in the conduct of government training and development program.
- Ćulibrk, J., Delić, M., Mitrović, S., et al. (2018). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job involvement: The mediating role of job involvement. *Frontiers in Psychology, 9*.
- Department of Education Order No. 32, s. 2011. Policies and guidelines on training and development programs and activities.
- Dreer, B. (2021). Teachers' well-being and job satisfaction: The important role of positive emotions in the workplace. *Educational Studies, 1*–17.
- Dhull, P., & Verma, G. (2017). Environmental education in teacher education and challenges. *Research Journal of Business Management, 2*, 84–87.
- Elrehail, H., Harazneh, I., Abuhjeeleh, M., Alzghoul, A., Alnajdawi, S., & Ibrahim, H. (2020). Employee satisfaction, human resource management practices, and competitive advantage: The case of Northern Cyprus. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics, 29*(2), 125–149.
- Ertürk, R. (2022). The effect of teachers' quality of work life on job satisfaction and turnover intentions. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research, 9*(1), 191–203.
- Fernandez-Docallas, F., & Batani, R. (2019). Working conditions and turnover intentions of teachers in small public junior high schools of Baguio City.
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research, 18*(1), 39.
- Guest, D. (2017). Human resource management and employee well-being: Towards a new analytic framework. *Human Resource Management Journal, 27*(1).
- Hair, J. F. (Ed.). (2017). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)* (2nd ed.). Sage.
- Hair, J. F. (2019). *Multivariate data analysis* (8th ed.). Cengage.
- Hair, J. F., Howard, M. C., & Nitzl, C. (2020). Assessing measurement model quality in PLS-SEM using confirmatory composite analysis. *Journal of Business Research, 109*, 101–110.
- Hazeen, F. M., & Umarani, C. (2022). Fairness in human resource management practices and engineers' intention to stay in Indian construction firms. *Employee Relations*. Advance online publication.

- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135.
- Hom, P., & Shaw, J. (2017). One hundred years of employee turnover theory and research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 102.
- Hoppock, R. (1935). *Job satisfaction*. Harper.
- Huang, I.-C., Du, P.-L., Wu, L.-F., Achyldurdyeva, L., & Wu, L.-C. (2021). Leader-member exchange, employee turnover intention, and presenteeism: The mediating role of perceived organizational support. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 42(2), 249–264.
- Hult, G. T. M., Hair, J. F., Jr., Proksch, D., Sarstedt, M., Pinkwart, A., & Ringle, C. M. (2018). Addressing endogeneity in international marketing applications of partial least squares structural equation modeling. *Journal of International Marketing*, 26(3), 1–21.
- Hussain, A., Khan, M. A., & Hussain, J. (2020). Interplay of organizational commitment and turnover intention in the academic sector. *Review of Economics and Development Studies*, 6(2), 401–412.
- Ijigu, A. (2015). The effect of selected human resource management practices on employees' job satisfaction in Ethiopian public banks. *EMAJ: Emerging Markets Journal*, 5.
- Iqbal, Q., Xuecheng, W., & Saina, B. (2022). Factors affecting employee retention: Integration of situational leadership with social exchange theory. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13.
- Isaac, K. D., Jingzhao, Y., Isaac, A. M., & Alfred, Q. (2020). Human resource management practices and employee turnover intentions nexus: Does the mediating role of job satisfaction matter? *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 8(1), 1–15.
- Islam, M., & Akter, T. (2019). Impact of demographic factors on job satisfaction: A study of private university teachers in Bangladesh. *SAMS Journal (India)*, 13, 62–80.
- Jehanzeb, K., & Bashir, N. A. (2013). Training and development program and its benefits to employee and organization: A conceptual study. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 5(2).
- Kamau, O., Muathe, S., & Wainaina, L. (2021). Demographic factors and turnover intentions of teachers in public secondary schools in Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 10(4), 363–374.

- Khan, G. F., Sarstedt, M., Shiau, W. L., Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Fritze, M. P. (2019). Methodological research on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An analysis based on social network approaches. *Internet Research, 29*(3), 407–429.
- Kooij, D. T., & Boon, C. (2018). Perceptions of HR practices, person-organization fit, and affective commitment: The moderating role of career stage. *Human Resource Management Journal, 28*, 61–75.
- Kirilova, K., Fu, X., & Kucukusta, D. (2020). Workplace design and well-being: Aesthetic perceptions of hotel employees. *The Service Industries Journal, 40*(1–2), 27–49.
- Kumar, D. (2019). Impact of compensation factors on teachers' job satisfaction: An econometric focus. *Global Disclosure of Economics and Business, 5*.
- Kume, E. (2020). Demographic factors and job satisfaction among teachers in lower secondary schools in Albania. *Journal of Education and Practice, 1*(1).
- Kunter, M., Kleickmann, T., Klusmann, U., & Richter, D. (2013). The development of teachers' professional competence. In *Teacher quality, instructional quality, and student outcomes* (pp. 1–22). Springer.
- Lazzari, M., Alvarez, J. M., & Ruggieri, S. (2022). Predicting and explaining employee turnover intention. *International Journal of Data Science and Analytics, 14*, 279–292.
- Likoko, S., Ndiku, J., & Mutsotso, S. (2018). Influence of demographic characteristics on turnover intentions among academic staff in public diploma teacher training colleges in Kenya. *International Journal of Science and Research, 27*(1), 62–87.
- Mabaso, C. M., & Dlamini, B. I. (2017). Impact of compensation and benefits on job satisfaction. *Research Journal of Business Management, 11*, 80–90.
- Mason, S., & Matas, C. P. (2015). Teacher attrition and retention research in Australia: Towards a new theoretical framework. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 40*(11).
- Mehrez, A., & Bakri, A. (2019). The impact of human resource practices on job satisfaction and intention to stay in emerging economies: Model development and empirical investigation among high-caliber governmental employees in Qatar. *Management Science Letters, 9*(3), 425–442.
- Miranda, N., & Fernando, W. R. P. K. (2020). The impact of human resource management practices of managers on perceived organizational

- performance: A study on Ceylon Fisheries Corporation in Sri Lanka. *Open Access Library Journal*, 7, 1–21.
- Mudor, H. (2011). Conceptual framework on the relationship between human resource management practices, job satisfaction, and turnover. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 2(2), 41–49.
- Muhangi, G. T. (2019). Demographic factors as antecedents towards turnover intention among secondary school teachers in Mbarara District. *Journal of Education & Practice*, 10(20).
- Nane, M. (2019). Impact of compensation practices on employee job satisfaction: Case of private banks in Sodo Town. *International Journal of Research in Economic and Social Sciences*, 9(5).
- Nawaz, M., & Pangil, F. (2016). The relationship between human resource development factors, career growth, and turnover intention: The mediating role of organizational commitment. *Management Science Letters*, 6(2), 157–176.
- Nhema, N., & Mutenheri, E. (2016). Factors that influence the turnover intentions of employees in the tourism sector in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 5(12), 158–165.
- OECD. (2019). *TALIS 2018 Results (Volume I): Teachers and School Leaders as Lifelong Learners*. OECD Publishing.
- Oludeyi, O. S. (2015). A review of literature on work environment and work commitment: Implication for future research in citadels of learning. *Journal of Human Resources Management*, 2(5).
- Onesmus, K., Muathe, S., & Wainaina, L. (2021). Demographic factors and turnover intentions of teachers in public secondary schools in Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 10(4), 363–374.
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42, 533–544.
- Parbudyal, S., & Natasha, L. (2010). Pay satisfaction, job satisfaction, and turnover intention. *Relations Industrielles / Industrial Relations*, 65(3), 470–490.
- Paşaoğlu, D. (2015). Analysis of the relationship between human resources management practices and organizational commitment from a strategic perspective: Findings from the banking industry. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 207, 315–324.

- Pule, S., & Mwesigye, J. (2014). Human resource policy and job satisfaction of employees in knowledge-based enterprises: A study of Kampala International University, Uganda. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 2(3), 13–27.
- Rajput, S., Singhal, M., & Tiwari, S. K. (2016). Job satisfaction and employee loyalty: A study of academicians. *Asian Journal of Management*, 7(1), 105–110.
- Rasool, S. F., Samma, M., Wang, M., Zhao, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2019). How human resource management practices translate into sustainable organizational performance: The mediating role of product, process, and knowledge innovation. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 12, 1009–1025.
- Rawashdeh, A. M., & Tamimi, S. A. (2019). The impact of employee perceptions of training on organizational commitment and turnover intention. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 44(2/3), 191–207.
- Ray, S., Danks, N. P., Valdez, A. C., Estrada, J. M. V., Uanhoro, J., et al. (2022). *semnr: Building and estimating structural equation models (2.3.2)*. CRAN R Project. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=semnr>
- Reza, N. M., & Alam, M. F. (2022). HRM practices and operational performance at jute spinning mills in Bangladesh. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management and Technology (AJMT)*, 2(3), 43–52.
- Ronfeldt, M., Loeb, S., & Wyckoff, J. (2013). How teacher turnover harms student achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 50(1), 4–36.
- Salama, W., Abdou, A., Mohamed, S., & Shahata, H. (2022). Impact of work stress and job burnout on turnover intentions among hotel employees. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19, 9724.
- Schuberth, F., Rosseel, Y., Rönkkö, M., Trinchera, L., Kline, R. B., & Henseler, J. (2022). Structural parameters under partial least squares and covariance-based structural equation modeling: A comment on Yuan and Deng (2021). *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 1–7.
- Silaban, N., & Syah, T. Y. (2018). The influence of compensation and organizational commitment on employees' turnover intention. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 20(3), 1–6.
- Siregar, D. M., & Maryati, T. (2020). Effect of compensation towards turnover intention with work as intervening variables a study at PT Madya Karya Putra. In *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research* (Vol. 176, pp. 340–345).

- Shuls, J. V., & Flores, J. M. (2020). Improving teacher retention through support and development. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, 4(1).
- Song, K. (2021). Well-being of teachers: The role of efficacy of teachers and academic optimism. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 831972.
- Tayyar, K. (2014). *Job satisfaction and motivation amongst secondary school teachers in Saudi Arabia*.
- Torlak, N. G., & Kuzey, C. (2019). Job satisfaction and performance links in private education institutes of Pakistan. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 68, 276–295.
- Toropova, A., Myrberg, E., & Johansson, S. (2019). Relationship of job satisfaction and turnover intention. In *Relationship of Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention* (pp. 71-97).
- Uddin, M. J., Miah, A. S., Rahman, M., & Rahaman, S. (2017). Mediation role of job satisfaction on HRM-Operational performance relationship: A three-way moderation effect by gender. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 51(3), 437–452.
- Ullah, H. (2016). School teaching as a feminine profession: the legitimization and naturalization discourses in Pakistani context.
- Vangel, K. (2011). *Employee responses to job dissatisfaction* (Seminar Research Paper Series, Paper 37). https://digitalcommons.uri.edu/lrc_paper_series/37
- Vermeeren, B., Steijn, B., Tummers, L., et al. (2014). HRM and its effect on employee, organizational and financial outcomes in health care organizations. *Human Resources for Health*, 12, 35.
- Wamukuru, D. K. (2016). Modelling the effects of teacher demand factors on teacher understaffing in public secondary schools in Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7, 147-153.
- Weiss, L. (2018). Building trust in higher education: An interview with Dr. Michele Williams. *Quarterly Review of Work-Life Policy and Practice*, 1-13.
- Wickham, H. (2016). *ggplot2*. Springer International Publishing.
- Yousef, D. A. (2017). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction and attitudes toward organizational change: A study in the local government. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 40(1), 77-88.
- Yunikawati, N. A., Kurniawan, D. T., & Rakhmad, A. N. (2021). The impact of HR practices on job performance and turnover intention with psychological well-being as a mediator in professional workers at a subcontractor telecommunication company in Indonesia. *KnE Social Sciences*, 5(8), 59–71.

- Zhenjing, G., Ku, C. S., Nassani, K. A. A., & Haffar, M. (2022). Impact of employees' workplace environment on employees' performance: A Multi-Mediation Model. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10.
- Zhong, Y., Zhang, H., & Wu, X. (2022). Predicting and explaining employee turnover intention. *International Journal of Data Science and Analytics*, 14, 279–292.
- Zwick, W. R., & Velicer, W. F. (1986). Comparison of five rules for determining the number of components to retain. *Psychological Bulletin*, 99(3), 432–442.

7. APPENDIX

Appendix 1

Table 8. Constructs effects on using bootstrapped PLS-SEM.

Path	Original estimate	Bootstrapped mean	Bootstrapped SD	2.5% CI	97.5% CI	VIF
TD -> JS	0.121	0.126	0.071	0.018	0.249	1.739
TD -> TI	0.295	0.292	0.090	0.142	0.435	1.791
CP -> JS	0.065	0.068	0.050	-0.012	0.153	1.323
CP -> TI	0.126	0.135	0.124	-0.064	0.344	1.338
PWE -> JS	0.729	0.722	0.060	0.617	0.815	1.995
PWE -> TI	-0.060	-0.057	0.155	-0.313	-0.197	3.837
JS -> TI	-0.114	-0.126	0.137	-0.350	-0.096	3.538

Note: A 10,000 bootstrap subsamples were used in the estimation process. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was used to identify potential collinearity issues. Critical collinearity issues likely occur if VIF is > 5.